

prime (arché)-law (unit) SENSE (Liä Dsi) principle:
(inter)actio ~ Hamiltons ~ H-Theorem ~ causa finalis
~ bifurcat. (~ singular.) pán best sover.-signif.-pure:
kalá symbios(ūn) ~ cósmos ~ Ω-point ~ harmon.

P-N ~ ±: Feed: back control (~ circular causat.) [- causality]:
Values ~ Behaviour: e.g.: order/chaos ~ intermittency
~ exaptation ~ superpos. ~ regulations ~ probab. ~ dyn. balance

~ stress (compensate.) ~ compromise ~ consider.
~ ±unfree: space ~ t (~ immat.)
~ complex. (~ laws) ~ flow (~ vortex)

Neg.: disorder/order ~ adaptation ~ neg. ~ duties ~ eschatology ~ dysbalance

~ conservation ~ brain network
~ pattern (~ structure) [formation]

~ mat. ~ rough society ~ ordinary matter ~ seeming ~ conscious
~ cultural selection ~ ontogenet. variabil. ~ genome ~ genet. ~ preimprinting
~ degeneration (~ weaknesses) ~ rehabilitat. need ~ ↓purificat. ~ saprobie
~ convent. ~ Trickle-down ~ deflat. ~ rezess.(depress.) ~ reregul. ~ postgrowth
~ less develop ~ artificial ~ involution ~ ontogenesis ~ unfolded
~ therapy ~ Yin-Yang ~ addiction (drugs) [pollution] ~ ill ~ poison ~ ±: truth ~ real. ~ wisdom ~ kindness ~ moderate
~ anergy ~ chaos (~ risk) ~ dyssymm. ~ random ~ bounded: I ~ H
~ insecurity (~ fear) ~ unsaturated ~ essential needs ~ show ~ typis.
~ competition ~ K-strategy (~ r) ~ logarithm. Spiral ~ monocultures
~ exterior ~ personality disorders [e.g.: evil ~ defence mechanism ~ interdepend ~ synth. ~ integr. (Sorokin) ~ good(ness)
~ cold empathy ~ narcissistic ~ bipolar ~ compulsive (~ obsessive)] ~ cosmo-indiv. ~ interest ~ sukha ~ benefaction
~ destructive molecular bond ~ molecular orbital bond {~ evolvement ~ vital. (~ Platon) [~ bios] ~ pollut. principle
~ war (~ violence ~ conflict ~ mistrust ~ crisis ~ coincid. ~ pain) ~ aim ~ evolution ~ vision ~ syntopy ~ real utopy
~ pressure ~ centric ~ mania: ego ~ techno ~ positiv. ~ ruthless ~ cosmogenesis(gony) ~ cosmic network
~ extensive quantities ~ external friction (~ resistance) ~ dysergie (~ membrane) ~ fulguration [~ pattern
(~ structure) format. ~ bifurcat. (cascade)]}
~ Reynolds number Re > Re_k ~ instabil ~ irregular
~ order parameter < 0,5 ~ Re >> Re_k ~ Re_k = chaotic turbulent ~ ±G ~ EM ~ m-h e. ~ emergence ~ fulgurat. ~ agens
(e.g.: Re_k, krit. ≈ 1 = degree of turbulence)] ~ attractor: chaot. ~ local
~ unequal spatially temporally complex. ~ unfree: space ~ t
~ binding (~ constraints) [~ interaction forces] ~ depend.
~ entropy S ~ -F(kT) ~ η ~ ζ ~ t ~ -Ω_T ~ φ ~ Φ ~ P ~ t
~ resources intensive use ~ quant.>qual. degrowth
~ quant.-mechan. ~ superficially expand
~ matter (~ down ward: reimmateral.) ~ explicatio
[~ e.g.: degrowth ~ resorption (resorbient)]
~ dream sleep ~ insomnia ~ restless(ness) ~ nightmare ~ Glu
~ insens. ~ unfeel. ~ cool(ness) ~ confrontat. ~ extrins.
~ hard: matter ~ ware ~ skills ~ functionalities ~ feelings 1. Order ~ structure ~ Bible ~ Veden ~ Koran ~ epen
~ destruction (~ disruption) ~ establishment ~ exovations ~ imitation ~ act. ~ amorphous ~ anomaly ~ shadow
~ dysgeneracy ~ imperf. ~ over-complex ~ habit ~ let ~ compensation action: religion ~ satisfaction
~ ignorance ~ eror ~ misbelief (~ false fetish ~ golden calf: e.g.: technic ~ market ~ ego ~ hedonist.
~ property ~ addictions ~ liberal ~ growth) ~ evil ~ lie ~ deception ~ hybris ~ depress. ~ doping
~ tumour {early stages} [- cancer] ~ unfreedom (~ constraints) [- dependences] ~ ugly ~ mad(ness)
~ bondage ~ disparity ~ unsolidarity ~ injustice ~ business as usual ~ grocer soul ~ estrangement ~ control
~ paradigm (~ injunction)] ~ duty ~ respons. ~ liable ~ status quo ~ reform ~ deal ~ worse ~ less ~ bourgeoisie
~ escapism ~ attitudes (codex) ~ classes ~ conceit (~ arrogance) ~ fatalism ~ fanaticism ~ nihilism ~ indoctr. ~ happiness

~ order param.: fct. η = functional F {η(r)T}
~ xýntropy (~ ±E) ~ partition function Z
~ order param.: fct. η = functional F {η(r)T}
~ unifers. φ(±Ω_T) ~ (P) ~ f(Ω) ~ H-functional
~ phil. of nature: ontolog.: eidet.-teleolog.
~ significat. ~ (im)material ~ complicatio
~ sensitivity ~ DMN (~ brain/gut) ~ ↔ metabol.
Glu-Gln-cycle ~ agent ~ feelings ~ states ~ processes
~ conservation ~ brain network
~ pattern (~ structure) [formation]
~ be hav. ~ moderate ~ ±control
~ ±trans(volution) ~ character ~ (self)realizat.
~ symm. breaking (~ branching) ~ rebellion
~ morphogenesis ~ ±anomalía ~ ±perfect.
~ less or more ~ anagoge ~ synflux ~ ±real
~ ±trat. [cybernet. feedback (control) cycles]
~ substitute (act) ~ gain ~ interact. circles
~ cosmo-indiv. ~ interest ~ sukha ~ benefaction
~ evolution ~ vision ~ syntopy ~ real utopy
~ cosmogenesis(gony) ~ cosmic network
~ (structure) format. ~ bifurcat. (cascade)]}
~ emerging (e.g.: economy: markets)
~ (apo)kálýpsis ~ ±collaps (~ Pi-Code) ~ Faust I
~ approach ~ scaling) ~ interpersonal
~ trans behaviour (relation) ~ synrevers.
~ syngenet. ~ s-e (~ bio) dyn. ~ conditioning ~ sex
~ chron. stress (~ burn out) [- neurasthenia]
~ enligntment ies (permanent) ~ kósmogenesis
~ transimmanent ~ syngenesis ~ hypersynthesis
~ mereo th. ~ ana(logy) ~ parallel. ~ coevolut. ~ coincid.
~ causa efficiens ~ determin. chaos
~ uncondit. + statist. Laws (~ cond. prob.)
~ Bible ~ Veden ~ Koran ~ epen

~ more (over) developed (e.g.: economy: countries) ~ illegitim (~ il)legal ~ iniquity ~ excesses ~ intransparence ~ euphemist. ~ etikette ~ neurot. ~ melancholy ~ insults ~ secular

~ kalýptein ~ (caste) kratia: e.g.: Oligo ~ Fisko ~ Mono ~ Phobo ~ Mafia ~ patronage ~ Organism. Crime ~ oligarchy ~ lower drives (e.g.: instinct, power abuse, control constraint)

Positive: Feed: back (~ reinforcing loop) ~ for
[~ upward causation] {~ bottom up}: e.g.: order/disorder
~ pre-adaptat. ~ harmonis. ~ balance ~ calm(ness) ~ equival.
~ immat. ~ naturisat. ~ vacuum ~ unconscious ~ pos. ~ righs
~ phylogen. variat. (~ biodiversity ~ redund.) [~ mutability]
~ natural selection ~ epigenetics ~ postimprinting ~ biomic
~ regeneration ~ prerehabilitat. (e.g.: gut flora) ~ katharobie
~ re: vitalis. ~ naturalis. ~ cultiv. ~ socialis.
~ bio: oikonomia (~ economics): para. ~ solidar. ~ selective
~ Trickle-up ~ inflat. ~ common welfare ~ prosper. ~ deregul.
~ develop ~ natural ~ evolution ~ phylogenesis ~ folded
~ complem. ~ prophyl. ~ Yin-Yang ~ wu wei ~ TAI-CHE(I)
~ curare (~ Orthomolecular Medical) ~ fasting (~ autophagy)
~ Yoga ~ Meditat. ~ Ayurveda ~ TCM ~ decontaminate
~ sustainable (~ lasting) [(UN)SDG] ~ subsistence ~ coop.
~ synergie ~ arête ~ eudaimonia ~ sympathy ~ synwell
~ sovereign ~ supreme(um) [- hypostasis ~ pure(ness)
(~ Plotin: hypostase: phýseis: nous/psyche = to hen)]
~ exergy ~ order (~ cert.) ~ symm. ~ necessity ~ free: -I ~ -H
~ security ~ saturated ~ to be ~ identity ~ origin(är)
~ altruistic ~ r-strategy (~ g) ~ golden spiral ~ tolerance
~ interior values ~ spiritual (~ sublim.): e.g.: warm empathy
~ relaxat. ~ quiet ~ "memento mori" ~ progrestarine ~ recreat.
~ constructive molecular bond ~ molecular orbital antibond
~ selfless (~ transparence) [-peace] ~ purposeless
~ consens ~ trust ~ binding ~ considerate ~ pos. stress
~ intensive quantities ~ internal friction (~ resistance)
~ frictionless ~ laminar ~ attractor: period. ~ global
(~ Re < Re_k ~ order parameter > 0,5
~ stabil ~ regular ~ Re << Re_k = laminar)
~ equal spatially temporally complex. ~ free: t ~ space
~ degrees of freedom (independ.) ~ self-org.(order)[regulat.]
~ negentropy -S ~ F (free E) ~ statistical pot. Ω ~ Ω_T(η)
~ V(ζ) ~ φ ~ a ~ ζ ~ events Ω (-Ω_T ~ φ ~ Φ ~ P ~ t)
~ quant. > qual. growth ~ resources extensive use
~ qual.-eidet. ~ profounder-supremes-signific.
~ dysmat. (~ demat.) ~ ethereal ~ myths ~ mystics ~ implicatio
~ deep sleep ~ silence ~ boredom ~ monotony ~ GABA
~ sensibility ~ impulsive ~ spontan. ~ intrins. ~ mirror neurons
~ soft: matter ~ ware ~ skills ~ capabil. ~ feelings 2. Order
~ creations ~ startups ~ innovations ~ inspirative
~ morphous ~ nomaly ~ regeneracy ~ perfect. ~ under-complex
~ becoming (~ Heraclitus) ~ change ~ do ~ re-ligio
~ (self)knowledge ~ alernea ~ good ~ beauty ~ sharing ~ transpar.
~ liberate ~ equal. ~ solidar. ~ just (~ fair) ~ (self)regulat.
~ novelty ~ revolution ~ paradigm (~ injunction) shift
~ better ~ supremes ~ wider ~ profounder ~ multum, non multa
~ opulent ~ generalization ~ quicker ~ inefficient ~ apagoge
~ efflux (~ elevation ~ animist. ~ irrational ~ irreal)
~ surplus ~ acquire ~ supply ~ slow food
~ independent ~ liberare(lis) ~ eleutheros ~ positiv. ~ optim. ~ anarchy
~ idea ~ (trans) self-determin. ~ autonomy ~ underdeterm. ~ ex ante
~ well kósmos krátos ~ proairesis (Aristoteles) ~ pessim. ~ prevent.
~ joy ~ ananda ~ (self)love ~ curiosity ~ kindness ~ compassion
~ unconvet. ~ creative ~ safety ~ natural. (~ Aristot.) ~ skeptic ~ intuit.
~ genesis: natural ~ bio ~ culture ~ utopy ~ techn. ~ genuine ~ extrapolat.
~ antigravity ~ light electrons ~ static interact. ~ filament ~ submergence
~ less (under) development (e.g.: economy: countries) ~ legitim ~ discrimin.
~ apo-kalýptein ~ an-cratia ~ values: supremes-profounder-signif.-integr.
[~ e.g.: original ~ authent. ~ ident. ~ powerless ~ uncontrol ~ restructure
Pi-Code)] ~ imagine ~ magic ~ erot. ~ UrFaust
~ approx. (~ compactificat.) ~ revers. ~ epigen. ~ endocrinology
~ trans (inter) [pre] personal ~ universal hypergoods ~ renaissance
~ agenz ~ allopoiesie ~ accomodation (e.g.: plural., freedom, altruist.)
~ enlightenment i.w.s ~ kósmos ~ kósmosophrosyne ~ transzendent
~ hypergenesis ~ supersynth. (e.g.: normal hierarchy ~ holon ~ holarchy) ~ toto
~ homogeny ~ convergence ~ homology ~ correspondence ~ homokósmo
~ correlat. ~ post hoc ~ causa formalis ~ stochast. ~ deduct.
~ concomitance- and functional laws ~ descriptive ~ Kalama sutta
~ sermon on the mount ~ construct. behaviour maxim
~ economical ~ small is beautiful (~ little but fine) ~ efficient ~ epagoge ~ reflux [- reduction. ~ spiritual(ist.) ~ rational ~ real] > clans ~ strains ~ monetary ~ wrong ~ complicate
~ (neo)liberalism [~ e.g.: (turbo)capitalist. (hyper)consume ~ religious select ~ Puritan. ~ Calvinist ~ protestant. ethics ~ intensiv. ~ success ~ power ~ precariat ~ speculat. ~ isolat.]
~ Neo-Feudalism ~ Tribut economy ~ rentiers ~ Fin.-Military-Industr.-Data-Pol.-Legal legitimated complex ~ A: Social-Eco-Liberal ~ conformism ~ inferiority complex ~ demand
~ subject behaviour ~ wolves in sheepskin ~ secret org. ~ elitist ~ manipul. ~ subtil ~ trivial ~ rudimentär ~ aftercare principle ~ Parkinson Law ~ Peter Principle ~ order muffy
~ decline (~ decadence) ~ totalitar. ~ tyranny ~ despotism ~ dictatorship ~ autocrat. ~ authority ~ dogmat. ~ ideology ~ fundamental. ~ overdeterm. ~ ex post ~ in deficit ~ abstine
~ democracy: local ~ direct ~ base ~ deliberative ~ consens (Hume) ~ affected (~ sufferer) ~ privileg. (elite) ~ conspiracy ~ synarchie ~ echo chamber ~ comfort zone ~ niche
~ conformation ~ filter bubble ~ suffering ~ luck ~ hate ~ greed ~ discontent ~ provocation ~ aggression ~ panourgia (Plato : euthydem) ~ passion(less) ~ euphemist. ~ vulgar, bad
~ condition. ~ programming ~ legalist. (~ dogmat.) [- rights (jurist)] {~ Sophist.} ~ illiquid. (~ Pi-Code) ~ postfact. democrat. ~ fake news ~ propaganda ~ discursive (~ reflect.)
~ regress ~ step backwards: natural ~ bio ~ culture ~ dystopy ~ interpolat. ~ waste ~ abundance ~ Junkies ~ legalis. criminal. ~ porno ~ wrong impetus ~ veloziferisch ~ Faust II
~ gravity ~ magnetic interaction ~ heavy electrons ~ voids ~ emergence (~ more is different)
~ more (over) developed (e.g.: economy: countries) ~ illegitim (~ il)legal ~ iniquity ~ excesses ~ intransparence ~ euphemist. ~ etikette ~ neurot. ~ melancholy ~ insults ~ secular
~ kalýptein ~ (caste) kratia: e.g.: Oligo ~ Fisko ~ Mono ~ Phobo ~ Mafia ~ patronage ~ Organism. Crime ~ oligarchy ~ lower drives (e.g.: instinct, power abuse, control constraint)
~ differ. ~ iterat. (~ renormizat.) ~ irrevers. ~ genet. ~ toxif. ~ mind disease (misery) [cold] ~ conceal ~ subtle alienation ~ incapacitate ~ heteron. ~ subversive ~ charismat.

~ hyperagenz (~ solipsism) ~ anything goes ~ ego hypergoods (e.g.: liberty) ~ enlighten. ~ cosmos ~ cosmophysics ~ immanent ~ degeneration ~ dyssynthesis ~ pars ~ (self)destroy
~ pathology ~ hierarchy ~ heterarchy ~ heterogen (inhomogen) ~ divergence ~ illusion ~ lack of impulse (self)control ~ self-enrichment ~ affective disordered superparasit (system)
~ spiral: misallocation ~ injustice ~ (social) exclusion ~ disincentives ~ intentional (system. [calculate] misery (impoverishment) ~ exploitation ~ disparticipat. ~ privileg. ~ project.
~ causal. ~ propter hoc ~ causa materialis ~ determin. ~ induct. ~ causal and teleologic explanations ~ normative ~ Torah (ten commandments) ~ deadly sins ~ destruct. Maxim
~ filzocratia ~ traumata (~ dissociationen) ~ t: bandit ~ slaves ~ manag. ~ is money ~ structural violence of the elites and the systems ~ mammon(ism) ~ corrupt

This graph show real dynamical nonlinear and non-equilibrium feedback networked circuits of comparable logistic processes in nature-bio-culture with scale invariance by scaling function for universal order parameter.